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CURRENT STATE OF KNOWLEDGE OF ESD IN ENVIRONMENTAL ENGINEERING PROFESSORS IN COLOMBIA.

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ABSTRACT

With this paper, we want to demonstrate the current state of knowledge of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) in the case of environmental engineering teachers in Colombia (South America). To determine the state of knowledge, a structured survey with 21 multiple-choice questions with the Likert scale scheme was used. The survey was applied to 39 university teachers who teach in environmental engineering programs, from 13 different universities. The survey also verified whether the Environmental Education (EE) trend is still being used by teachers and therefore transmitted to students. It was possible to identify a general lack of knowledge of ESD by teachers and, on the contrary, a strong preference for EE. This is largely due to the fact that, since 2003, Colombia has a policy that promotes EE, which has not had updates or derogations that give way to the ESD. It was found that teachers consider that ESD is important in the field of action of environmental engineers and that this educational trend must be part of the curriculum. Therefore, although the country has strong roots and promotes EE, environmental engineering professors see ESD as an alternative that would strengthen the skills of future engineers.

1. INTRODUCTION

Environmental engineering is one of the areas of engineering, in some countries it is postgraduate degree and in others, such as Colombia, it is an undergraduate degree. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) are a field of reference and they mark a

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milestone in the discussion on Sustainable Development (SD) [1]. It is expected that with this strategy, companies, communities and especially governments will advance in achieving SD [2]. With this, it is intended in an integrative way to reconcile the globalized economic and consumption model that prevails today, in a responsible model with the environment [3]. Education plays an important role in the promotion and training on the understanding of SD and especially the SDG, in this sense it has been highlighted that Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) is the model to achieve it [4]. ESD holistically addresses the three fundamental pillars of sustainable development: society, environment and economy [5]. From this, the ESD seeks the transformation of the person, their environment and society, and this change must be reflected in their way of thinking and acting, which will end up impacting all levels of society, in the end, promoting the scope of the SDG [6].

In universities, ESD responds to the need of the labor market where companies are increasingly interested in hiring SD literate graduates [7]. Therefore, higher education institutions have a duty to drive and promote the process of transition to sustainability through teaching, research and dissemination [8, 9]. ESD has increased more strength since the United Nations declared the decade for ESD between the years 2005 and 2014. Thanks to this, ESD is well knowledge in regions such as Europe and some parts of Asia. But it seems slight known in places like Latin America [11].

We find Environmental Education (EE), which has a much greater historical trajectory than ESD, but differ in their objective, ESD seeks to promote the relationship of SD with economy, society and environment, which is supported by economic growth [5]. On the other hand, the EE is characterized by being protectionist, by seeking the generation or awareness, for this reason it distances from consumerist economic models and economic growth [12, 13]. Environmental engineering in Colombia is characterized by being an undergraduate program, whose areas of application are mainly focused on solving problems associated with the quality and coverage of basic sanitation (drinking water, sewers, solid waste, etc.), still persistent problems in Latin America. This branch of engineering in Colombia is relatively recent, the first undergraduate programs appeared in the decade from 1990 to 2000 [14].

Within universities and therefore in undergraduate programs, teachers represent a key factor in promoting education and achieving environmental sustainability. There are different studies that show the support and research that teachers give in higher education around ESD [15]. Apart from the knowledge of ESD, teachers seek to impact students with the goal of achieve a social transformation from their professions [16]. This approach ensures that ESD has teachers as essential actors to achieve the SDG [17]. The challenge of transforming teaching is broad, since it represents making changes in disciplinary approaches so that they integrate social, economic, environmental and cultural aspects in each discipline. This challenge implies new study plans and curricula adapted for this purpose, and that in turn the teachers are trained and prepared within the universities [15, 18]. Engineering studies are a fundamental part of the range of the academic offer of universities; in turn they are engines of development through science and technology, finding the answer to contemporary problems of society, especially in terms of infrastructure [16]. In this sense, due to its

broad capacity to impact on urban and natural ecosystems, engineering companies are called to adopt ESD in their teaching and therefore, promote development in terms, not only technical and technological, but in a transversal way involving the environmental sustainability [19]. With this research, from a survey applied to 43 professors of environmental engineering programs from 13 Colombian universities, it was sought to establish the degree of knowledge of ESD and, therefore, infer the degree of transmission and impulse of this current towards students of this discipline. At the same time, we verified that EE is so deeply rooted in relation to ESD in teachers, that is, the preference that teachers have in relation to these two options or models of education.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Type and structure of the survey.

The survey was applied to 39 teachers from 13 Colombian universities that are part of environmental engineering programs. The questions were asked in a positive formulation. For the answer option, the horizontal Likert scale model was used. Questions of this style are structured in a request for an answer, followed by a statement and a rating scale to answer the question posed [20]. The choice of horizontality is given in order to avoid extreme response style (ERS), which tends to occur more frequently in vertical type options [21]. The scale used varies from 1 to 4, where 1 is equivalent to “not at all” and 4 is equivalent to “completely”, corresponding to a unipolar scale [22]. The survey includes 21 questions related to the subject of study, the survey is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Survey conducted between university teachers.

Q1	Are you or have you taught an undergraduate program in environmental engineering?	Q8	Have you carried out environmental education activities in your role as an environmental engineering teacher?	Q15	Have you ever applied ESD in your classes or subjects?
Q2	Of the objectives of environmental education, please indicate which one you consider would be the most important for an environmental engineer.	Q9	Have you ever been trained or guided in environmental education strategies outside of academic training activities?	Q16	Do you know the differences between Environmental Education (EA) and Education for Sustainable Development (ESD)?
Q3	How important do you think environmental education is for an	Q10	Do you think that within the field of action of the environmental engineer it is	Q17	In your opinion, you think that ESD focuses on actions for the environment.

	environmental engineer?		important to obtain tools to develop environmental education actions?		
Q4	How important is environmental education to you as a person?	Q11	Would you like to be part of the formulation and implementation of environmental education projects?	Q18	In your opinion; Do you think ESD focuses on cultural, social, economic and biological diversity?
Q5	As a teacher of the environmental engineering program, do you think you train your students in the concepts or principles of environmental education?	Q12	Do you think it is important that environmental education be involved within the Environmental Engineering program curriculum?	Q19	Do you think ESD is important within the field of action of the environmental engineer?
Q6	Do you consider that there are sufficient academic spaces (subjects) in the study plan where the environmental engineering student is trained in environmental education?	Q13	In your opinion, in which of the following academic contexts of the structure of the training of an engineer should environmental education be oriented?	Q20	Do you think it is important that ESD be involved within the Environmental Engineering program curriculum?
Q7	Do you consider that within the contents of the subject (s) that you teach, the student is trained in environmental education skills?	Q14	How well do you know the concept or current of Education for sustainable development?	Q21	As an engineering teacher, do you think you train your students in EDS principles?

2.1. Survey reliability

For the validation of the survey conducted between university teachers, the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was used, which determines the measure of internal consistency of a measurement instrument where several elements are included [23]. The value of the coefficient varies from 0 to 1, and it is divided into ranges that qualitatively interpret the instrument [24, 25]. As a result, an Alpha coefficient of 0.77 was obtained for the applied instrument, therefore, qualitatively it can be said that the consistency and reliability are good.

2.2. Sample and limitations

The total number of universities that offer EE undergraduate degrees are 46, of which 12 are accredited of high quality. High quality accreditation refers to the conditions of maximum educational quality in research, teaching and social responsibility, it is a voluntary process, different from the minimum quality conditions called qualified registration which is mandatory for operation, in both cases the government is in charge of giving the certifications [26]. The collaboration of 13 universities was achieved, which corresponds to 28%, of these, 6 are accredited, which corresponds to 50% of the total of accredited universities. In any case, there is a limitation in the application of the surveys, since many of these are not completed by the entire teaching staff of the program. Another limitation was to achieve certain universities that refuse to apply these instruments due to confidentiality or for other reasons not explained by their directives. It is important to mention that personal or institutional information was not requested in the applications and in the survey in order to protect the data and to guarantee a confidential response. The demographic characteristics of the teachers surveyed can be seen in the table 2.

Table 2. Characteristics of the teachers surveyed.

Ages		Undurgraduate degree	
Age groups (years old)	%	Engineers by training	%
20 - 25	2,3%	Biologist	20,9%
25 - 30	18,6%	Environmental engineer	25,6%
30 - 35	30,2%	Chemical engineer	7,0%
35 - 40	20,9%	Civil engineer	4,7%
40 - 45	11,6%	Agricultural engineer	11,6%
45 - 50	11,6%	Industrial engineer	2,3%
50 - 55	4,7%	Degrees in social sciences	27,9%

3. RESULTS

3.1. Qualitative questions

As shown above, three questions that do not include the Likert scale were asked, these were asked as multiple-choice, questions (Q1, Q2 and Q13). Regarding Q1, of the total of respondents ($n = 43$), 90% belonged to an environmental engineering undergraduate program ($n = 39$), in order to determine only the results of the people who are from this program. The responses of the 39 teachers were used for establishing some results and conclusions. In Q2, it is intended to establish which approach (practical, theoretical or practical-theoretical) they give when teaching, in this sense the following options were presented:

(a) hold people accountable and make people aware of the knowledge of the environment and its problems; (b) Involve people in the realities, practices and experiences of environmental problems that are perceived in their territories; (c) develop attitudes that help communities to strengthen their feelings of conservation and respect for nature and the environment, as well as their own culture; (d) develop skills that promote the search for solutions to current environmental problems and

prevent those that may appear in the future; (e) encourage individual or collective actions that solve or avoid environmental problems.

Option (b) was selected by 39.5% of the respondents, 27.9% selected option (d), 20.9 option (c), 7% option (a), and 4.75% option (e). Question Q13 refers to the opinion of teachers about the possible location of EE or ESD competencies in the curriculum, the possible options were (a) human sciences; (b) basic sciences; (c) basic engineering; (d) applied engineering. In this case, 39.5% answered option (d), 30.2% option (a), 16.3% option (c) and 14% option (b).

3.2. Quantitative questions

Table 3 shows the results and statistical values of the applied instrument, where f is the frequency. The value per item was determined, which is the sum of the values assigned to each response by the respondents. In other words, for this instrument the maximum value per item is 156, which would mean if all the people ($n = 39$), assigned a value of 4 (completely) to their answer in a question.

Table 3. Statistical values of the instrument.

Question	Value per item	$f(4)$	$f(3)$	$f(2)$	$f(1)$	(%) 4	(%) 3	(%) 2	(%) 1
Q3	151	35	3	1	0	90%	8%	3%	0%
Q4	151	34	5	0	0	87%	13%	0%	0%
Q5	135	22	14	2	1	56%	36%	5%	3%
Q6	113	11	15	11	2	28%	38%	28%	5%
Q7	121	12	21	4	2	31%	54%	10%	5%
Q8	128	18	15	5	1	46%	38%	13%	3%
Q9	115	18	8	6	7	46%	21%	15%	18%
Q10	147	33	4	1	1	85%	10%	3%	3%
Q11	148	33	5	0	1	85%	13%	0%	3%
Q12	148	32	6	1	0	82%	15%	3%	0%
Q14	120	15	13	10	1	38%	33%	26%	3%
Q15	107	12	11	10	6	31%	28%	26%	15%
Q16	115	14	12	10	3	36%	31%	26%	8%
Q17	112	10	17	9	3	26%	44%	23%	8%
Q18	134	20	16	3	0	51%	41%	8%	0%
Q19	150	33	6	0	0	85%	15%	0%	0%
Q20	148	32	6	1	0	82%	15%	3%	0%
Q21	121	12	19	8	0	31%	49%	21%	0%

It is important to mention that the mean value was not used as recent studies suggest not using this value for Likert scales, because the results come from different sources, that is, questions with different contexts [27]. The highest frequency is given in the value of 4 "completely" and the lowest in 1 "not at all" in most of the questions, except for some cases such as Q6, Q7, Q17 and Q21.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In general, for the survey conducted between university teachers from environmental education in Colombia, the individual analysis of the items or questions was avoided, therefore, this discussion, except in some relevant cases, will discriminate the answers to some questions. This study is based on the recommendations of Harpe (2015) for Likert scale instruments. We found a notorious attachment of teachers to EE, which indicates a clear and generalized ignorance of ESD. The answers to the questionnaire show a greater knowledge and clarity in concepts of the EE.

It can be seen from the results that teachers have no clear idea about the concept and usefulness of ESD. The question Q14 shows that only 38% of the teachers know it completely, 59% denote a certain degree of ignorance and 3% do not know this concept at all. In Q16 it is observed that the teachers are not completely sure about the differences between the EE and ESD currents. This could mean, among other things, a mixture of concepts, currents, and methodologies, gaps that will be transmitted to students. In turn, this can generate a clash between the model of sustainable development and conservationism. In this sense, students are not fully informed of the differences, advantages or disadvantages of each model. Knowing that ESD is the model to achieve the SDG [4], the results of this study help to affirm the low levels of progress that Colombia has compared to the SDG. This country recently ranked 9/12 in the Latin America region in the “2019 SDG index for Latin America and the Caribbean” [29].

The generation of conceptual gaps due to the incomplete transmission of information may be due to the fact that this country does not have an updated environmental education policy or a policy that promotes ESD. For the first case the document “Environmental Education Policy” dates from the year 1994 [14], this has a clear protectionist trait and urges all educational entities, from primary school to universities, to enact environmental education. On the other hand, there is no government document that promotes ESD in this country. All this makes to clearly promote the SD difficult for the universities and for these in turn to become an engine to achieve the SDGs. The foregoing evidences in the same way that contrary to what would be expected, universities in this country are not responding to professional needs, where graduates must be literate in SD [7].

It can be concluded that there is a consensus that EE and ESD are important in the teaching of environmental engineering. There is also an agreement that there should be a modification in the study plans. This option opens up the need to reform the curriculum and incorporate either of the two EDS or EE streams. In addition, it promotes the preparation and training of teachers, since the preparation of the subject pushes teachers to know and position themselves on one of the two streams.

It is important that in addition to what is presented, new research is sought that involves other academic actors, including students, managers, employers, and graduates. To know their perception and expand the results.

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